

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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俄罗斯经济吸引外商直接投资的现代方面分析
**ANALYSIS OF MODERN ASPECTS OF ATTRACTING FOREIGN
DIRECT INVESTMENT INTO THE RUSSIAN ECONOMY**

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摘要。在世界经济发展的现阶段，吸引外国直接投资被视为国家间商业合作的主要形式之一。在其他国家进行投资是为了克服对外贸易壁垒，并将生产公司设在关键市场。这使我们能够显著降低运输成本，并考虑到购买行为的特殊性和外国消费者的需求。在全球市场竞争加剧和制裁限制实施的背景下，吸引外国直接投资的决定性因素已成为生产资产的相对“便宜”和东道国劳动力的可用性。这项工作的目的是研究外国直接投资在国内经济形成和现代化中的作用，以及制定消除阻碍外资流动的障碍和改善我国投资环境的建议。为此，对吸引外国直接投资进入俄罗斯经济的主要趋势、机遇和问题进行了分析。此外，还制定了旨在提高这一过程效率和确保经济增长的建议。

关键词：外国直接投资、俄罗斯经济、发展、分析、机会、吸引力。

Abstract. *At the present stage of development of the world economy, attracting foreign direct investment is considered one of the leading forms of business cooperation between states. Investments are made in other countries in order to overcome barriers to foreign trade and locate production companies in key markets. This allows us to significantly reduce transportation costs and take into account the peculiarities of purchasing behavior and the needs of foreign consumers. In the context of increased competition in global markets and the application of sanctions restrictions, the determining factor for attracting foreign direct investment has become the relative “cheapness” of production assets and the availability of labor in host countries. The purpose of this work is to study the role of foreign direct investment in the formation and modernization of the domestic economy, as well as to develop proposals for eliminating barriers that impede the flow of foreign capital and improving the investment climate in our country. To achieve this, an analysis of the main trends, opportunities and*

problems of attracting foreign direct investment into the Russian economy was carried out. In addition, proposals have been developed aimed at increasing the efficiency of this process and ensuring economic growth.

Keywords: *foreign direct investment, Russian economy, development, analysis, opportunities, attraction.*

Introduction

The study of the possibilities of attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) for the development of the Russian economy is important and relevant due to their significant role in this process. Because FDI brings new capital, technology and expertise that can help improve productivity, competitiveness and innovation in the financial sector, it can be considered a key driver of a country's economic growth and development.

The tightening of economic sanctions by Western countries against Russia and the growth of geopolitical tensions in connection with the conduct of a special military operation (SVO) in Ukraine had a negative impact on the influx of FDI to Russia [15]. To overcome it, the Russian Government took a number of different measures aimed at improving the investment climate and attracting new volumes of FDI into the country's economy from friendly countries. These include improving the regulatory framework, providing tax and other benefits to investors, and promoting Russia's potential as an investment destination through various marketing and promotional activities.

The importance of attracting FDI to the Russian economy is determined by the availability of additional investment resources, the creation of new jobs, increasing export opportunities and increasing labor productivity. In the Russian financial system, attracting FDI helps to diversify sources of financing and reduce the cost of capital. In the manufacturing sector, attracting FDI helps accelerate the transfer of innovative technologies, create new jobs, develop infrastructure and accelerate economic growth. The presence of foreign investors in the Russian economy serves as a guarantee to other investors that the country is a safe place to invest [1, 3, 8, 14].

The current economic situation in our country is characterized by tightening sanctions restrictions, ousting Russia from the global capital exchange system and the associated shortage of financial resources, technologies and modern management methods for structural reforms and economic modernization [9, 12]. These factors determine the importance of attracting FDI to the Russian economy. At the same time, Russia today is considered by the world economic community to be a country with an attractive investment climate [2, 8]. To overcome the negative consequences of sanctions restrictions, our country needs to develop new measures to attract FDI in order to create long-term economic ties with friendly

countries, ensure an increase in the standard of living of the population, stimulate development and growth of domestic investment.

Materials and methods

For Russia, attracting FDI opens up new opportunities to stimulate economic growth in the country. Intensifying FDI inflows to Russia can contribute to a positive impact on the domestic economy in the following aspects:

1) in the extractive industries - to promote growth in production volumes, reduce the risk of losing access to foreign markets (in the context of tightening sanctions restrictions);

2) in the manufacturing industries - to promote the implementation of import substitution strategies and the growth of export volumes of products manufactured in Russia;

3) in the sectors of transport infrastructure - to promote the modernization and growth of efficiency of the transport network of our country;

4) in the Russian economy as a whole - to promote the development of new technologies, the introduction of more modern high-tech production and management systems, increasing the rate of economic growth of the country and investment activity, promoting the efforts of federal and regional government bodies to create a favorable investment climate in Russia and its regions [6].

Currently, the organizational and economic mechanisms for attracting FDI into the Russian economy are:

1) tax incentives;

2) improvement of customs administration;

3) the work of institutions for improving the investment climate (Russian Direct Investment Fund (RDIF), Russian Investment Agency (RIA), Agency for Strategic Initiatives (ASI), Agency for Export Credit and Investment Insurance, Advisory Council on Foreign Investment in Russia and investment ombudsmen);

4) the work of regional agencies to attract investments, including foreign capital;

5) implementation of federal target programs, the use of which makes it possible to concentrate resources on solving priority complex problems, create the necessary infrastructure of territories and a favorable investment climate in the regions of the country, combine the efforts of federal, regional bodies and the private sector of the economy, ensure a high degree of transparency of government procurement and orders within program events;

6) introduction of a public-private partnership (PPP) mechanism, through which the state has the opportunity to attract private, including foreign, funds to implement priority projects and stimulate the development of innovation [7];

7) Investment Fund of the Russian Federation, which provides state support by co-financing investment projects on contractual terms with the formation of prop-

erty rights of the Russian Federation, providing state guarantees to the Russian Federation for investment projects;

8) special economic zones (7 industrial-production, 5 technology-innovation, 14 tourist-recreational and 3 port SEZs) [13], where favorable conditions apply [10];

9) “road maps” (action plans of the “National Entrepreneurial Initiative” to improve the investment climate in Russia, namely: simplification, reduction in cost, acceleration of procedures that are crucial for doing business) [11].

Results and discussion

However, due to the aggravation of the problem of attracting FDI to Russia, these mechanisms require effective structural changes and the development of new recommendations and measures to enhance the influx of FDI into the domestic economy. At the same time, the new tools for attracting FDI to Russia should be based on the internal potential and national advantages of our country. Taking them into account will help minimize weaknesses that impede the influx of FDI, identify and prevent threats to reduce their inflow and make the most of existing opportunities. To specify these processes, a SWOT analysis of the key success factors, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the national economy on the way to attracting FDI was carried out (see Table 1).

Based on the results of the SWOT analysis, we can conclude that, despite the intense competition to attract FDI into national economies between developing countries, Russia has good chances and advantages over its competitors. These advantages should be realized as much as possible, both at the federal and regional levels.

*Table 1
Results SWOT Analysis*

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large domestic market; • Availability of qualified specialists; • Favorable economic and geographical location; • Resource potential of the country; • Propensity of the bulk of the population to consume; • Growth of industrial production; • Active development of regions; • Increased investment attractiveness of the constituent entities; • The work of institutions to improve the investment climate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater dependence of the economy and the state budget on raw material revenues; • Deformation of the industrial sector; • Weak focus on the competitiveness and quality of products of local enterprises; • Immature competitive environment; • Difficult geopolitical situation; • Low innovative potential; • Insufficiently developed infrastructure.

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversification of the Russian economy; • Presence in the top 20 ratings of investment attractiveness (Doing Business); • Direction of investment in priority industries (in the manufacturing sector, in the mechanical engineering industry, high-tech innovative industries); • Financing and development of the necessary infrastructure; • Reducing administrative barriers; • Optimization and unification of the legal and regulatory field; • Implementation of “road maps” to stimulate entrepreneurial and investment activity, simplify doing business, and reduce administrative barriers; • Effective implementation of targeted programs; • Active promotion of the investment attractiveness of Russia and its regions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The focus of most of the capital investments of foreign investors on the raw materials industries; • Slow implementation of new legal and regulatory standards; • Lack of new technologies for production, level of competitiveness of industrial products; • Slow growth of the country’s investment potential; • Further political destabilization on the world stage; • intensification of competition with other countries for attracting foreign capital; • FDI outflow.

The priority direction in the field of FDI inflow into the Russian economy is to direct them to those sectors where the effect of their application will be greatest. However, at present there are discrepancies between the directions of FDI flows in the industry and the needs for their development in these industries. Therefore, modernization of the material and technical base of Russian industry with the help of FDI will be successful if foreign capital is directed to those sectors in which the effect of its use will be greatest. To determine the priorities for FDI in industries and sectors of the Russian economy, it is necessary to develop a methodology for selecting FDI recipient industries, taking into account the need for FDI and competitiveness.

In the context of a sectoral analysis of the Russian economy, it is necessary to keep in mind the complexity of the growth and development of industries, that is, to identify industrial complexes of interconnected production (clusters) around key industries, including the service sector. The further formation of such clusters with the participation of FDI will increase the multiplier effect in related industries.

Based on the results of the analysis of the use of industry priorities for FDI inflow, the following recommendations can be proposed:

1. Direct FDI to those sectors that will allow you to accumulate income in a short time and increase the tax base.

2. Encourage and stimulate the influx of FDI into key industries that have the greatest multiplier effect (mechanical engineering, automotive, chemical, pharmaceutical industries, etc.).

3. Increase the efficiency of attracting FDI, based not only on the need of industries for their influx and their technical potential, but also on the possibility of increasing the competitiveness of the domestic economy in the global market.

When considering the current state of FDI in Russian regions, the problem of their uneven distribution was identified. The structure of FDI incoming to Russia is deformed, with most of it concentrated in a limited number of regions with strong geographic and sectoral unevenness of distribution. There is a significant strengthening of the role of the largest regions (Moscow, Tyumen region, Moscow region, St.-Petersburg, Sverdlovsk region, Sakhalin region, Leningrad region, Krasnoyarsk region) and a reduction in the share of the rest in the total volume of incoming FDI.

The dynamics of the distribution of the total volume of incoming foreign direct investment in the regions of Russia by federal district for 2010-2023 confirms that the bulk of it is concentrated in the regions of the Central Federal District (about 70%) (see Table 2) [4]. It owes its dominant position and stable first place to the city of Moscow, whose role is exaggerated. However, over the analyzed period of time this share decreased by 4.75%. In this process, over the past 10 years there has been a downward trend in FDI volumes in value terms. Structural and dynamic changes indicate a tendency towards an increase in the degree of heterogeneity in attracting FDI across Russian regions.

The results of the analysis of incoming FDI by federal districts show that there are differences in the investment attractiveness of regions and the geographic focus of FDI, and that some regions with a favorable investment climate do not fully realize their own potential. This is especially true for the Republic of Tatarstan, which is one of the three most attractive regions among the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, along with Moscow and St. Petersburg [5]. These regions are among the leaders in attracting FDI due to a combination of “hard” and “soft” factors that influence the investment attractiveness of the region (see Table 3).

Table 2
Distribution of the total volume of incoming FDI by federal districts

Districts	Number of regions	Share of incoming FDI, as a percentage of their total volume		Absolute deviation in 2023 from 2011
		2011	2023	
Central	18	74,73	69,98	-4,75
North-Western	10	7,03	6,64	-0,39
Southern	6	1,05	0,68	-0,37

North-Caucasian	7	0,10	0,06	-0,04
Privolzhsky	14	2,28	1,48	-0,80
Ural'sky	4	9,10	15,52	6,42
Siberian	10	2,15	2,50	0,35
Far Eastern	11	3,56	3,14	-0,42
Total	80	100	100	0

Source: calculated by the authors based on Rosstat data.

Table 3
Factors influencing the investment attractiveness of the region

«Hard» factors	«Soft» factors
Geographical position	Interest of the regional administration in FDI
Natural resources	Managing Investor Expectations
Work force	Successful experience in implementing
Physical infrastructure	investment projects with FDI
Scientific and technical base	Reducing administrative barriers
Availability of quality human capital	Legal environment
Volume of the domestic consumer	Financial and tax incentives
goods market	Communications between government and
Volume of the domestic market for	business
industrial goods	Professional business support

Based on an analysis of the combination of “hard” and “soft” factors, difficulties and problems that foreign investors face in most regions of Russia, a set of recommendations has been developed for regional authorities in order to increase the influx of FDI into the regions of Russia and the country as a whole:

1) optimization of the organizational structure of cooperation with foreign investors, compliance with the “one window” principle, increasing transparency and efficiency;

2) conducting marketing and providing comprehensive, up-to-date information through electronic services;

3) modernization and development of infrastructure taking into account the requirements of investors;

4) development of public-private partnerships (especially for the creation of technology and industrial parks, infrastructure modernization), development of regulatory legislation with established forms and responsibilities of each participant in this partnership;

5) development of clear criteria and procedures for obtaining financial and tax benefits;

6) provision of benefits in accordance with the interests of investors;

7) providing support to international companies from friendly countries;

8) creating infrastructure for innovation and attracting foreign investors to R&D, increasing the level of education in the regions;

9) creation of a mechanism for exchanging experience in attracting FDI between regions of the Russian Federation;

10) identification of priority industries in the regions and the development of clusters in them with an emphasis on cooperation between local and foreign companies.

The implementation of the proposed measures will create a favorable investment climate in the Russian regions and will help eliminate the main difficulties that foreign investors face in modern conditions and increase the influx of FDI into the regions of the Russian Federation.

Ensuring sustainable economic development of the regions of our country is one of the important directions of economic policy pursued in the Russian Federation. Attracting FDI is directly related to the development of regional economies, their investment attractiveness and relative advantages. The initiative to increase the attractiveness of Russian regions for foreign investors should be implemented comprehensively at the federal and regional levels of government. To ensure economic growth and the influx of FDI into Russia, it is necessary to develop a set of measures aimed at creating a favorable investment climate. In our opinion, such measures should include:

1) development of political and economic cooperation between Russia and friendly countries;

2) carrying out competent macroeconomic policies to reduce inflation, increase the rate of economic development, increase labor productivity, etc.;

3) the formation of measures to increase the investment activity of Russian enterprises and the country's population;

4) implementation of measures to combat corruption;

5) creation of special financial national institutions, specialized funds, insurance companies capable of insuring foreign capital against political, investment, commercial and financial risks;

6) development of a guarantee system that effectively protects the property of foreign investors;

7) further liberalization of the tax system and the introduction of additional tax incentives in order to stimulate the influx of FDI into the Russian economy;

8) development and implementation of a set of mechanisms for state support of innovation and investment projects that are aimed at modern high-tech production;

9) reducing the administrative burden by reducing bureaucratic procedures;

10) taking measures to improve the efficiency of legislation and create uniform rules of the game for all market participants.

In the context of growing competition for attracting FDI, the use of incentive measures for foreign investors becomes especially important. The proposed

recommendations and measures of a tax, financial and organizational nature for Russia and its regions are intended to improve the investment climate of the country and enhance the investment attractiveness of both the national economy as a whole and its individual industries and regions. Ultimately, this will ensure an increase in the volume of innovatively filled foreign direct investment in Russia to update and modernize the material and technical base of the Russian economy.

Conclusion

In modern conditions, Russia is faced with a set of problems that complicate the prospects for our country's participation in international capital exchange in the context of increasing the efficiency of attracting and using FDI. For FDI to enter the domestic market, it is necessary to eliminate problems such as administrative and trade barriers, insufficient innovation potential, opaque interpretation and application of laws, low degree of protection of property rights, and insufficiently developed infrastructure. Eliminating the above problems and reducing their negative impact will ensure an influx of FDI into the Russian economy. This requires an innovative structure of foreign investment, changes in the system of state regulation of foreign investment, its mechanisms, tools and other components. To ensure economic growth and the influx of FDI into Russia as a whole, a set of measures has been developed that will help create favorable market conditions in Russia:

1) improving the macroeconomic situation in the country and developing relations and developing political and economic cooperation between Russia and friendly countries;

2) improving the quality of legal regulation of investment activities by taking measures to: increase the transparency and efficiency of legislation, create uniform rules of the game for all market participants; development of a guarantee system that effectively protects the property of foreign investors; reducing trade and administrative barriers;

3) involvement of the state in investment activities through the creation of national financial institutions, specialized funds capable of insuring foreign capital against political, investment, commercial and financial risks; development and implementation of a set of mechanisms for state support of innovation and investment projects that are aimed at modern high-tech production;

4) implementation of incentive measures to support foreign investors: fiscal incentives (tax holidays, benefits for activities related to R&D, income tax benefits, etc.), financial incentives (provision of preferential loans or loan guarantees, provision of preferential conditions for state insurance etc.) and other incentives (improving investment infrastructure, creating zones with a special economic status).

Ensuring sustainable economic development of the regions of our country is one of the important areas of economic policy pursued in the Russian Federation,

in connection with which the author has developed a set of recommendations for regional authorities in order to increase the influx of foreign direct investment into the regions of Russia:

- 1) optimization of a transparent and effective organizational structure for cooperation with foreign investors, compliance with the “one window” principle;
- 2) development of public-private partnerships, development of legislative norms regulating this type of partnership with established forms and responsibilities of each participant in this partnership;
- 3) providing benefits in accordance with the interests of investors in them (benefits for land and state financing of infrastructure facilities), creating infrastructure for innovative activities, increasing the level of education in the regions;
- 4) providing support to international small and medium-sized companies;
- 5) creation of a mechanism for exchanging experience in attracting foreign capital between regions of the Russian Federation.

These recommendations and principles, which are based on previously identified problems and barriers to investment activity in Russia, in general, and in its regions, in particular, will increase the influx of FDI and improve the efficiency of the system of state regulation of investment activity in our country.

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